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Work Package 6

Informatics platform and Knowledge Engine (PaaS, SaaS)

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Executive Summary

This document provides a full view of the capabilities of the Knowledge Engine within the Human Exposome Assessment Platform (HEAP). This document describes the data management, data warehousing, data sharing and integration with the Information Common. It provides a encompassing description of the data analysis, feature store, machine learning and pipeline orchestration capabilities. The implementation presented here is coordinated within the Informatics platform and Knowledge Engine Work Package (WP 6) and its goal is to provide to users a comprehensive set of data analysis and machine learning tools together with easy, controlled access to the data stored in the Information Commons as well as the possibility to publish results back into the Information Commons.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose

This document provides guidance for the development of Data Analysis and Machine Learning Pipelines through the use of the Data Analytics and ML capabilities of the Knowledge Engine implemented through the Hopsworks platform within the Human Exposome Assessment Platform (HEAP). This document describes the technical architecture, data flow, data analysis and associated metadata and means for accessing data from the Information Commons.

1.2 Overview

HEAP[1] aims to provide a system for collecting, managing, sharing and ultimately analysing exposome related data, as defined in the project proposal. The Knowledge Engine ensures that access to sensitive data is according to the permissions set. We still strive to encourage collaboration through sharing of data, once again, as long as the permissions are correctly adhered to.

Key aspects facilitated by the Knowledge Engine are:

- projects as a shared workspace to enable collaboration for data scientists
- a feature store for curating, storing, sharing and discovering helpful features
- multiple model training framework support together with provenance information for each exploration of experiments
- a model registry for storing, sharing, serving and monitoring of models
- a scalable and consistent metadata layer
- user definable tags as flexible, structured metadata

All the code related to the HEAP platform will be part of the HEAP-EXPOSOME organization on Github: <https://github.com/HEAP-EXPOSOME>.

1.3 Structure of the document

The structure of the document is as follows:

- Chapter 1 (this chapter) introduces the document, its purpose and a list of acronyms and abbreviations
- Chapter 2 introduces the data management of the Knowledge Engine as well as the authentication and authorization mechanism for both internal access to data, as well as access to sensitive data stored in the Information Commons.
- Chapter 3 provides an overview over the data analysis and machine learning capabilities of the Knowledge Engine
- Chapter 4 describes the metadata layer of the Knowledge Engine.
- Chapter 5 describes the integration plan between the Hopsworks platform as the Knowledge Engine implementation and the services provided under the Information Commons

2. Data management

2.1 Hopsworks data management

Hopsworks uses two main abstractions for handling data and these are *datasets* and *projects*. A cluster can have many projects and each project can be seen as a grouping around data (datasets), users (team members), programs and services. The project abstraction allows users to easily identify their own workspace and what data can be accessed by both users and services.

Within the projects, we employ role-based access control (RBAC). This is a well-known security model that enables administrators to give a group of users the same access rights to selected resources. An administrator can thus define a single security policy for a role and apply it to multiple users within his department. However, users might be members of multiple departments and they might also change departments during their time at the institution. Dynamic role-based access control means that, based on some other policy, you can change the set of roles a user can hold at a given time.

Hopsworks implements a dynamic role-based access control model through a project based multi-tenant security model. The policy for deciding the role a user holds at a particular time is determined by the project the user is currently accessing. Dynamic role-based access control prevents a user from cross-linking or copying data between two different projects, as each access within each project would be defined as different roles.

Every project has an owner with full read/write privileges and zero or more members. The members can have two type of roles within the project:

- data owner - the default role for the user that creates a project and this role offers the highest privileges within the project. The users can access all the services and have access to all the operations that can be applied to data - create/delete/read/write/share/unshare. This user category also has access to modifying the composition of the project team by adding or removing users from the team.
- data scientist - users added to the project with this particular role have a reduced set of privileges, as they can only read data and they are not allowed to manage the project membership.

One user within a project can thus be a member of multiple projects, and inside of each project this user will have a unique identity - we call it project-user identity, which is effectively a role. Each user thus has multiple roles, but only one role can be active at any specific time. As we can see in the figure 1, if Alice is a member of two projects: Project_A and Project_B, she would have a separate identity associated within each project: Project_A_Alice and Project_B_Alice.

Figure 1 - Hopsworks role based access control

Access control policies are implemented by the platform services:

- files/directories permissions for our file system HopsFS, Hive[2] and the offline Feature Store
- Kafka[3] ACLs using a Hopsworks project-based authorizer plugin
- Elasticsearch[4] Open Distro[5] permissions using a Hopsworks project-based authorizer plugin[6]

2.2 Hopsworks data access

A fundamental principle in every distributed system is that processes exchange messages over the network or through shared state (file system or database). When sending messages over the network, it is imperative that we validate the identity of the sender and also protect the messages from adversaries reading or modifying their contents.

Hopsworks use X.509 certificates to authenticate and authorize users. Certificates enabled us to use the well established TLS protocol to provide confidentiality and data integrity. Every user and every service in a Hopsworks cluster has a private key and an X.509 certificate.

Figure 2 - Hopsworks Service Authentication and Authorization

Hopsworks comes with its own root Certificate Authority (CA) for signing certificates internally. Hopsworks root CA does not directly sign requests, instead it uses an intermediate CA to do so. To protect against a security breach, more than one intermediate CA can be made responsible for a specific domain. As can be seen in the figure 3, there is one intermediate CA for creating API and Kublet certificates and another intermediate CA for user, application, and service certificates inside Hopsworks.

The Hops intermediate CA supports three kinds of certificates: User, Application and Service certificates. They are all signed by the same intermediate CA, but have different lifespan and attributes.

All backend services exchange messages with each other and for this we make sure we do encryption in transit. Both servers and clients require all communication to be done over TLS with 2-way authentication, that is both entities should present a certificate.

Hopsworks and Elasticsearch (Open Distro) use JWT authentication. HopsYarn issues a token for each submitted job and propagates it to running containers. The JWT are rotated automatically before they expire and they are invalidated once the application finishes.

Figure 3 - Hopsworks Public Key Infrastructure

2.3 Hopsworks data sharing

A dataset is the main abstraction over data stored in the distributed file system of the platform (HopsFS) and is the main data abstraction that can be shared between projects. In particular, sub-directories and individual files cannot be shared between projects. Hive databases and Feature Stores are represented as datasets within a project and thus can also be shared between projects.

Hopsworks datasets can be easily shared and unshared in an effort to usher collaboration on the platform. The dataset sharing mechanism makes use of the

underlying access control list (ACL) mechanism provided by the file system HopsFS and makes sure that users within the cluster have at all times access to particular files only if they are members of projects that should have access to this data.

As we can see in the figure 4, members of both Project_A and Project_B can now jointly access the shared resources such as Feature Store, Hive DB and Elasticsearch Indices.

Figure 4 - Hopsworks sharing of assets

2.4 Hopsworks new Data Catalogue

As part of task 6.3 we have created a new catalogue for Hopsworks items which includes at the moment the data items - projects, feature groups and training datasets.

Figure 5- New UI - Projects Listing

As we can see in the figure 5, the new UI can currently list all the projects present in the platform and provides methods to view and modify metadata associated with it, such as name, description, summary of contents - feature groups and training datasets, activity.

When we navigate to one of the projects, as we can see in the figure 6, we can view the sections for data: feature groups and training datasets as well as the auxiliary section - storage connectors which helps configure elements in the feature groups section. Another section is the Jobs section which contains the definitions of applications in the form of jobs and the executions of these applications.

Project overview [Project Settings](#)

On this project, your access role is **Data owner**

A demo project for getting started with featurestore [edit description](#)

Last updated	Created on	Feature Groups	Training Datasets
3 days ago	2021-06-14 15:36:56	7	1

Data owners: Data scientists: [edit members](#)

Shortcuts

Nothing pinned

- + Create New Feature Group
- + Create New Training Dataset
- 🕒 Documentation

Recently opened

- 📄 season_features_on_demand #19
- 📄 attendances_features #16
- 📄 teams_features #18
- 📄 games_features_hudi_tour #14

Figure 6 - New UI - Projects Details

demo_fs_meb10000 Admin Admin

Find a feature group... sort by last created [New Feature Group](#)

7 out of 7 feature groups displayed

● **season_features_on_demand #19**

Features of games, on demand feature group example

Version	Creation	Last updated
1	2021-06-14 15:46:35	3 days ago

● **teams_features #18**

Features of football teams

Version	Creation	Last updated
1	2021-06-14 15:46:19	3 days ago

● **players_features #17**

Aggregate features of players football teams

Version	Creation	Last updated
1	2021-06-14 15:44:13	3 days ago

Figure 7 - New UI - Feature Groups Listing

If we navigate to the feature groups sections, as we can see in the figure 7, we can view a listing of all the feature groups together with elements that allow us to view metadata and other elements associated with feature groups, such as description, activity, statistics and preview of a sample of data.

If we select one of the feature groups, as we see in the figure 8, we can view the details of it, and this includes, but is not limited to the list of features contained, provenance information related to how the feature group was created or is being used, validation rules, tags, statistics and activity.

Figure 8 - New UI - Feature Group Details

2.5 Information Commons Authentication

The developed service components (see section 3) utilise ELIXIR[7] AAI[8] to authenticate the user and authorise the data use. ELIXIR AAI is a service provided by ELIXIR and meant for life-science researchers around Europe. ELIXIR AAI supports over 500 research organisation credentials, which means that researchers can use their home organisation credentials to log-in to the service. ELIXIR AAI also implements the global standards, such as OpenID Connect[9] and GA4GH Passport[10].

To authorise the data use, the service components utilise GA4GH Passport standard.

2.6 Submission Engine

As Specified in the Reference Architecture (D10.1) in order to utilise data in the Knowledge Engine it first needs to go through Information Commons (IC) via the Submission Engine (SE). This is achieved by data custodians, which can utilise ETL jobs to remove identifiable information from the data, create subsets or any necessary additional processing as well as data encryption in order to make data available to the Information Commons.

It is important to distinguish between two types of data in the Information Commons:

1. **work data** - (raw anonymized) data, represents the most frequent type of data used in computations, in the Knowledge Engine pipelines in order to derive insights.
2. **publish data** - depicts data identifiable via a permanent identifier (such as a DOI (Document Object Identifier)[11]) that researchers can use in their publications for referencing purposes. However this data can be used to derive insights as well in combination with other *work* or *publish data* or even both. Knowledge Engine can be used to generate this kind of data.

The Submission Engine will interface with the Information Commons via an API that facilitates storing sensitive data in an encrypted format.

Sensitive Data (SD) Connect represents the service that will provide such an interface with the storage server CSC Allas[12]. From the technical point of view, Allas is a modern object storage system. It comes with the Swift (S3-like)[13] interfaces on a CEPH[14] storage.

SD Connect represents:

- a central hub through which the user can respectively process and publish sensitive data in Information Commons;
- the interface to upload and temporarily store sensitive data in CSC Allas storage solution;
- an easy to use solution for sharing work data between different users during the research project.

2.7 Information Commons

The HEAP Information Commons (IC) represents the data repository infrastructure that provides data. It includes both the physical resources to store and archive HEAP data and the interfaces to make this data available to the Knowledge Engine. The researchers will not interact directly with the Information Commons, but only through the Knowledge Engine, as its role is to facilitate on-demand access to the data (in a federated setup this implies the data remains at their respective source).

This is achieved via combination of services and physical infrastructure:

- **ePouta**[15] - represents a virtual private cloud designed to meet the security requirements for handling sensitive data. It runs on the OpenStack[17] cloud software.
- **SD-Desktop** - is a service providing secure access over public internet to ePouta virtual private cloud, and allowing secure analysing of sensitive data remotely from users' own computer via a web browser. In order to access files stored in the Information commons access a FUSE filesystem is set up on demand
- **SD-Submit** - is designed to facilitate storing in Information Commons the **publish data** type for long term storage, and register a Data Access Committee to manage access to it.

Figure 9 - Information commons and Hopsworks in ePouta

With Sensitive Data Remote Desktop (SD Desktop) a user, or a group of users, will get his/her own private workspace, where he/she can securely process sensitive data, which can be in any format. This data can be further processed in the Knowledge Engine.

In order to achieve this secure computing environment where IC can work together with KE (Hopsworks) we need to take advantage of the SD-Desktop and ePouta cloud infrastructure so that users can connect to a Hopsworks services running on the secure cloud infrastructure - as depicted in *figure 9*.

SD Submit service all the tools necessary to facilitate the metadata description and to authorize **publish data** type access and reuse. The data access committee will stay in control of this data. The service provides a permanent identifier (DOI) that you can use in your publications for reference purposes. The metadata model used in this service corresponds to ENA (European Nucleotide Archive) Metadata Model[18].

2.8 Entitlements Management System

The Entitlements Management System is a service component responsible for managing the entitlements - access rights - in the system. The Entitlements Management system is a tool that concentrates on two goals:

- Facilitate data access as security and rights management without making data access cumbersome;
- Manage access rights to resources and provide traceability of the data access rights granted.

REMS[19] (Resource Entitlement Management System) is an open source tool for managing access rights to different kinds of resources. REMS enables users to apply for access rights easily and offers a secure way for the data owners to manage access to their data.

The resources in REMS do not necessarily have to be electronic data sets. It is possible to manage access to basically anything, as long as it is identified by some form of an identifier. This includes for example research datasets and biological samples.

Figure 10 - REMS Application process

Figure 11 - GA4GH Passports[20]

REMS can produce and consume cryptographically signed GA4GH Visas that assert a user's access rights.

In the language of the GA4GH specifications, REMS acts as a *Passport Visa Assertion Repository*, *Passport Visa Issuer* and *Embedded Token Issuer*. The permission information is relied to the *Passport Broker* (e.g. Elixir/Life Science AAI) and can be retrieved on demand by KE aided by the use of JWT[52].

The interface implies that KE will always ask AAI providers to facilitate the JSON Web Tokens required for data access. The GA4GH Passports specification defines within this JWT what data the user can use via the GA4GH Visa. This ensures the KE can

check the user's identity and entitlements across locations (distributed installations of KE and IC).

Another option to this design would be connecting directly to REMS with the drawback that other *Passport Visa Issuer* cannot be queried for permissions, in the case permissions are recorded in a distributed fashion at different Data Access Committees.

3. Knowledge Engine

Data science applications in the domain of Big Data and Deep Learning typically involve running multiple applications in a pipeline fashion, with the output of previous stages feeding into the next stages as input. This is done in order to make sure that each application encapsulates its own logic, is easily maintainable and can be re-scheduled for execution when changes occur in code or input data. The stages typically part of a Deep Learning Data Pipeline are:

- Data Ingestion
- Data Preparation
- Data Validation
- Feature Extraction
- Model Training
- Model Serving
- Model Monitoring

Figure 12 shows a typical Deep Learning pipeline and the stakeholders involved in each of these stages.

HORIZONTAL SCALABILITY AT EVERY STAGE IN THE PIPELINE

Figure 12 - Machine Learning Pipeline

This pipeline, however, is not executed just once and instead, there are multiple iterations of it starting with experimentation and exploration leading to a model artifact that is further refined and updated even after deploying to production as time passes

by and more data and use cases are collected. Therefore, a data life cycle is formed, which continuously iterates the ML pipeline. The Hopsworks platform tracks provenance information related to the different executions of your pipelines through file system tracked - implicit provenance[50]. With implicit provenance we make sure that metadata and data are always coupled and there is no orphaned metadata left on data deletion.

Data engineers and data scientists are faced with the complex task of developing the workflows to accommodate this life cycle and thus, in order to ease this work Hopsworks provides a robust and flexible architecture. Figure 13 presents the overall architecture and lifecycle of a Deep Learning Pipeline along with the technologies used to implement it and presented in the rest of this document.

Figure 13 - Hopsworks ML Lifecycle

The stages of data ingestion, pre-processing, validation and management of a service can all be considered as part of the Data Engineering cycle. In the case of Hopsworks, the Feature Store is the service used to manage this part of the pipeline, dealing with managing curated feature data.

Once a data scientist has a service that supports curating and managing features, naturally, the next large step is actually training a model. A natural first stage in the training model part is fetching the feature data and materializing them in the

appropriate file format that the model training framework expects. Of course, training a model is not always the first try first success type of event, and this requires a lot of experimentation and exploration. Of course in order to speed the process, this experimentation is typically done on smaller relevant samples and not the whole dataset. This exploration stages of the model design includes ablation studies, hyperparameter tuning which will be presented in more detail in later sections of this document. These stages can include large amounts of variants of the model and it is expected that once again, the platform would help the user in running, managing and extracting the best models from all of these trials. Once the model also passes the validation phase, it can be registered in the model registry in order to be deployed to production. This whole workflow of designing and developing models iteratively until the appropriate model is finally pushed to production can be considered the Data Science lifecycle.

Once a model is mature enough to move into production, there is another set of infrastructure elements that need to be orchestrated, managed and monitored. One of the main goals of a Deep Learning Pipeline is the perpetual refinement of the production ready models through the use of specific user defined metrics. In order to detect when changes to the model are required, a monitoring mechanism is in place that logs all inference requests and tracks how the model performs over time. The Model Serving and Monitoring stages are part of the ML Engineering Life Cycle.

From the perspective of services involved, Figure 14 shows the entire service stack with the core services HopsFS and RonDB[21] (NDB/Mysql Cluster) providing a horizontally scalable data and metadata layer. Apache Hadoop Yarn and Kubernetes[22] provide a resource management layer where applications can be run within the Hopsworks platform. These applications can be pure Python applications or they can utilize distributed processing frameworks such as Apache Spark[23] and Apache Flink[24]. In order to improve development speed even further, many of these applications can also be run in a Jupyter notebook environment. Auxiliary services including the ELK stack[25], Graphana[26] and Prometheus[27] provide logging, monitoring and full text search capabilities. As described above, Machine Learning Pipelines are complex and Hopsworks integrates Apache Airflow[28] as an orchestration engine of these pipelines[29]. On top of all these services, Hopsworks, the web application provides a REST API[30] that enables users and client applications to connect and communicate with the whole Hopsworks cluster.

Figure 14 - Hopsworks services stack

3.1 Running Applications

As we have seen above, Machine Learning Pipelines consist of a number of stages and each of these stages can be re-executed multiple times. In Hopsworks each stage is a separate application which can be defined as a job and each time a job is executed it is tracked as a separate job execution. Another method to run applications is as Jupyter Notebooks. Notebooks can be seen as an exploratory environment for both data and code and when both data and code are ready, they can be transformed to Jobs that can be scheduled and re-executed whenever necessary. As pipelines contain multiple stages and each stage is defined as a separate job, we use Apache Airflow to orchestrate a whole pipeline and make sure each stage is executed if and when the previous stage completes and its output is ready to be consumed. Applications in Hopsworks can be written to take advantage of the spark or flink distributed frameworks, they can be pure python jobs or they can be more generic Docker[31] job and thus can run anything that can be packaged in a Docker container.

3.1.1 Python centric analysis

Python is the preferred programming language for machine learning applications and thus Hopsworks provides extensive support for it. Numerous machine learning libraries exist in python in order to support the work for data scientists, such as Pandas, Numpy, Scipy or for machine learning such as TensorFlow and Pytorch. However, there is a problem with the way python libraries are installed, which makes it difficult to manage and synchronize python environments for multiple users over multiple machines in a cluster. Each library installed can of course come with its own dependencies and if each user is allowed to install the library version they need, it would most probably corrupt the programming environment of another user.

In order to provide a level of isolation between the work of different users and to reduce the problems which might arise from dependency conflicts, Hopsworks makes use of Anaconda[32] environments. Anaconda is an open-source distribution of the Python and R programming languages for scientific computing. Since Hopsworks aims to provide an environment where collaboration is a core part of the workflow, it chose to provide an Anaconda environment per project which is then shared by the members of that specific project.

Upon creating a new Project in Hopsworks, a new Anaconda environment is created and set to use Python 3.7. This environment already comes pre configured by Hopsworks to each the work of developing machine learning applications and comes with Tensorflow, Python, Keras, scikit-learn preinstalled. Hopsworks aims to ease the workflow of its user, so they don't have to waste time figuring out which versions they have to use for each dependency in order to get all these libraries to function within the same environment. More so, these environments are present on any machine in the cluster, and if the machine also provides GPUs, Hopsworks will install the correct CUDA version compatible with the Tensorflow and Pytorch versions.

Users can then install any other library they want through pypi, conda, git or by uploading any .whl, .egg, requirements.txt or environment.yml file. This provides the users with a great flexibility in setting up their own project's environment.

Figure 15 - Python environment library installation

When installing libraries using Conda, users can change the *default* channel that we use, if their favourite library resides in a different channel.

From the manage environment tab, the users can also see all installed libraries and of course uninstall any library in order to maybe instal a newer version of it. Some libraries are marked as pre-installed and cannot be managed by the users, as they are set by the platform itself in order to provide compatibility with other libraries and hardware infrastructure, such as GPUs.

Channel	Library	Version	Package Manager	Status	User-Installed
conda	_libgcc_mutex	0.1	CONDA	INSTALLED	Uninstall
pypi	absl-py	0.12.0	PIP	INSTALLED	Uninstall
pypi	aiohttp	3.7.4.post0	PIP	INSTALLED	Uninstall
pypi	argon2-cffi	20.1.0	PIP	INSTALLED	Uninstall
pypi	asn1crypto	1.4.0	PIP	INSTALLED	Uninstall
pypi	astunparse	1.6.3	PIP	INSTALLED	Uninstall
pypi	async-generator	1.10	PIP	INSTALLED	Uninstall
pypi	async-timeout	3.0.1	PIP	INSTALLED	Uninstall
pypi	attrs	21.2.0	PIP	INSTALLED	Uninstall
pypi	autovizwidget	0.15.1	PIP	INSTALLED	Uninstall

Figure 16 - Python environment library listing

If one of the installed libraries brings dependencies that might conflict with the current environment, the user will get warned in order to take appropriate action.

In order to provide reproducible results, the whole project's environment can be exported as a yml file which can then be used to set up a new project for a whole new team working on a different cluster.

```
name: theenv
channels:
  - pytorch
  - defaults
dependencies:
  - _libgcc_mutex=0.1=main
  - blas=1.0=mkl
  - ca-certificates=2020.10.14=0
  - certifi=2020.12.5=py37h06a4308_0
  - freetype=2.10.4=h5ab3b9f_0
  - intel-openmp=2021.2.0=h06a4308_610
  - jpeg=9b=h024ee3a_2
  - lcms2=2.12=h3be6417_0
```

Figure 17 - Python environment export as yml file

3.1.2 Jupyter Notebooks

The preferred code development environment for data scientists are read-eval-print loop (REPL) environments. These REPL environments have recently become very popular, with the most popular of them all being Jupyter Notebooks[33]. Users can write code in their preferred language, provided there is a Jupyter kernel for that particular language. Once users execute code in Jupyter Notebooks, they can export the notebook containing the code and the output, which might be data visualizations, into, for example, pdf or html files which can be shared as a reporting outcome.

Jupyter Notebooks is a first class service in Hopsworks and is provided as a service in any project. As such, Hopsworks enables collaboration, as any member of the project team can read, modify or execute the notebooks connected to this particular project. There are two interfaces available, the classic Jupyter as well as the newer JupyterLab interface, which provides a richer set of interfaces and resembles more closely to an integrated development environment (IDE).

When starting the Jupyter Server, Hopsworks already provides a number of configurations which emphasize or set specific parameters, depending on what type of code the user wants to execute within the notebook. These configurations are:

- Python - running pure code
- Experiments:

- Experiment - make use of our utility libraries in order to run hyperparameter optimization on PySpark executors.
- Parallel Experiments - in addition to the above, users can run state of the art grid-search and differential evolution for hyperparameter selection.
- Distributed training - this new configuration setup involves making use of multiple machines with potentially multiple GPUs per machine in order to train machine learning models.
- Spark
 - Static - configure Spark with a fixed number of executors.
 - Dynamic - configure Spark to with a minimum and maximum number of executors and allow Spark to elasticity make use of the amount of executors it needs.

The configuration of a started Jupyter Server cannot be modified dynamically while the server is running. You can still view the configuration of the running Jupyter Server, but if you require a different configuration, you will need to stop the current server, change configuration and restart.

There are four Jupyter kernels currently available in Hopsworks:

- Python - executes Python 3.7 code
- Spark - executes Scala spark code and interacts with the cluster through spark-scala
- PySpark - executes Python code and interacts with the cluster through PySpark
- SparkR - executes R code and interacts with the cluster through spark-R.

3.2 Hopsworks Feature Store

Data warehouses centralize data in a single platform and then empower business analysts with visual tools, such as Tableau and Power BI so they can derive historical insights into the business. Data scientists, in contrast, build predictive models to derive data insights. The feature store is the data warehouse for Data Science - it is a central vault for storing documented, curated, and access-controlled features that can be used across many different models. The feature store ingests data from the research study's many different sources after transforming, aggregating, and validating the data. Feature pipelines need to be written to ensure that data reliably flows from existing sources and is available in a format ready to be consumed by ML training pipelines and models.

As we can see in the figure 18, there are three main abstractions stored in the Feature Store: features, feature groups and training datasets. Abstractions within the Feature Store are organized hierarchically. On the most granular level are the features themselves. Typically, feature groups represent a logical set of features coming from the same data source sharing a common primary key. Feature groups also contain the schema and type information of the features, for the user to know how to interpret the data. In order to be able to train machine learning models efficiently, the feature data needs to be materialized as a Training Dataset in the file format most suitable for the ML framework used. For example, when training models with TensorFlow the ideal file format is TensorFlow's tfrecord format.

Figure 18 - Entities in the Feature Store

The Feature Store is a dual database-system, to cover all machine learning use cases it consists of a high throughput offline storage layer, and additionally a low-latency online storage. The offline storage is mainly used to generate large batches of feature data, for example to be exported as training datasets.

There is no database fulfilling both requirements of very low latency and high throughput. Therefore, the Hopsworks Feature Store builds on Apache Hive with Apache Hudi[34] as offline storage layer and RonDB(NDB) as online storage. The offline feature store through Hudi's capabilities offers users the capability to time travel, a feature that is very useful when trying to debug or understand the executions of your ML pipelines[48].

Figure 19 - Online Feature Store

3.3 Data Streaming

When we want to productionize a particular model, and want to use it for inference, some features will have very low latency and they will need to be transformed within ms or arrival, but we will also have features residing on databases or data warehouses with less latency requirements. The Feature Store is a way of integrating these features together in a central location, where users can expect low latency for particular features used, for example, at inference time, while some others are ok with slightly higher latency, but better scaling and throughput, like for example when materializing features into training datasets as the preparation step for training your model.

Our Dataframe API makes sure that when the user writes a feature, it is pushed to both online and the offline Feature Store, if the user configured it so. Depending on the time requirements, the user can process the incoming data into features either in Flink Streaming, Spark Streaming, pure python programs or simple Spark programmes.

Figure 20 - Structured Streaming with Spark

As we can see in the figure 21, the features relevant to a part model can have different frequency of ingestion. Some real-time features might arrive with sub second frequency, while some features might be computed in a batch fashion, as a Spark job with a daily frequency. All of these features might be relevant to a user wanting to either train a model, or use these features for inference purposes on an already existing model.

Online applications use the online feature store to retrieve feature values with low latency to build feature vectors that are sent to models for predictions. In contrast to higher latency data warehouses, feature stores may be required to return feature vectors in single millisecond latency - only really achievable in row-oriented or key-value stores.

The typical access pattern for retrieving features is a key-value lookup, but if features are to be reused in the online feature store, then joins are again required. In RonDB, the database backing the online feature store, a small number of joins can be performed at very low latency.

Figure 21 - Streaming sources with different reporting windows

3.4 Data Validation

As model training is very sensitive to bad data (null values, outliers cause numerical instability, missing values), feature data should be validated before ingestion. Data validation frameworks, such as Great Expectations[35] and Deequ[36], have appeared to help implement feature pipelines that apply predicates (data validation rules) on all the features ingested into the feature store, ensuring high data quality in the feature store.

As part of Task 6.2 we integrated into our Feature Store a tool for validating all data before being saved. We have an internal library called HSFS[37] used to interact with the Feature Store, and currently the validation module included is based on Deequ, with ongoing work being done on including Great Expectations as well.

The process of performing feature validation can greatly vary in terms of implementation from among DL pipelines or among data engineers and scientists. A reason for this is that data validation is not a strict set of rules that need to be applied on ingested data, rather is a set of best practices and some common rules, derived typically from the domain of statistics.

Predefined validation rules present in our tool are:

1. Size: Assertion on the number of rows of a feature. Acceptable size for e.g. min: 500 and max: 1000
2. Completeness: Assertion on column completeness. Acceptable fraction of the data to be complete, e.g. min: 0.5 max: 0.8
3. Uniqueness: Assertion on the uniqueness of a single or multiple columns. Acceptable fraction of the data to be unique, e.g. min: 0.7 max: 1
4. Distinctness: Assertion on the distinctness of a single or multiple columns. Acceptable fraction of the data to be distinct, e.g. min: 1 max: 1
5. Unique ratio: Creates a constraint on the unique value ratio in a single or combined set of key columns
6. Distinct values: Assertion on the number of unique values of a column
7. Entropy: Creates a constraint that asserts on a column entropy. Acceptable entropy of the data, e.g. min: 0.6 max: 1
8. Minimum: Assertion on the minimum of a column. Acceptable minimum value in the dataset, e.g. min: 3 max: 3
9. Maximum: Assertion on the maximum of a column. Acceptable maximum value in the dataset, e.g. min: 100 max: 120
10. Mean: Assertion on the mean of a column. Acceptable mean value of the dataset, e.g. min: 200 max: 250
11. Sum: Assertion on the sum of the values of a column. Acceptable sum of all values in the dataset, e.g. min: 5000 max: 5000
12. Standard deviation: Assertion on the standard deviation of a column. Acceptable SD of the dataset, e.g. min: 3 max: 5

3.5 Hopsworks Model Training

In Hopsworks Model Training we offer a rich experiment API for data scientists to run their Machine Learning code, whether it be TensorFlow, Keras, PyTorch or another framework with a Python API. It provides features such as automatic versioning of notebooks and the python environment, parallel hyperparameter tuning algorithms, and managed TensorBoard.

Every time you run an application to train a model, an experiment artifact is created that includes both the traditional information a program generates (results, logs, errors) as well as ML-specific information to help track, debug, and reproduce your program and its inputs and outputs:

- **hyperparameters:** parameters for training runs that are not updated by the ML programs themselves;
- **metrics:** the loss or accuracy of the model(s) trained in this experiment;
- **program artifacts:** *python/pyspark/airflow programs*, and their *conda environments*;
- **model artifacts:** serialized *model objects*, *model schemas*, and *model checkpoints*;
- **executions:** information to be able to re-execute the experiment, including parameters, versioned features for input, output files, etc;
- **versioned features:** to be able to reproduce an experiment, we need the exact training/test data from the run and how it was created from the feature store;
- **visualizations:** images generated during training and score. Also use TensorBoard to visualize training runs - Hopsworks aggregates results from all workers transparently;
- **logs (for debugging):** model weights, gradients, losses, optimizer state;
- **custom metadata:** tag experiments and free-text search for them, govern experiments (label as 'PII', 'data-retention-period', etc), and reproduce training runs.

Using the *model* python module in the hops[38] library, it is easy to version and attach meaningful metadata to models to reflect the performance of a given model version. The Hopsworks Model Registry, is a service where all models are listed in addition to useful information such as which user created the model, different versions, time of creation and evaluation metrics such as accuracy. The Model Registry provides functionality to filter based on the model name, version number and the user that exported the model. Furthermore the evaluation metrics of model versions can be sorted in the UI to find the best version for a given model. In the Model Registry UI, you can also navigate to the experiment used to train the model, and from there to the train/test data used to train the model, and from there to the features in the feature store used to create the train/test data.

Figure 22 - Hopsworks Experiments

3.6 Maggy - Advanced Model Training Optimizations

Maggy[39] is a framework for efficient asynchronous optimization of expensive black-box functions in Hopsworks. In Hopsworks, Maggy is mostly used to run experiments for:

- Directed Hyperparameter Search (ASHA, Bayesian) on TensorFlow, PyTorch, ScikitLearn, XGBoost;
- Parallel Ablation Studies. Without changing your inner training loop in TensorFlow, evaluate (in parallel) the effect of regularization techniques;
- Unified Logging in Jupyter notebooks. In real-time, view logs for parallel HParam/Ablation study tasks from your Jupyter notebook.

Maggy introduces the concept of “*oblivious training functions*”[51] and as the figure 23 shows, it enables you to reuse the same training code whether training small models on your laptop or reusing the same code to scale-out[49] hyperparameter tuning or distributed deep learning on a cluster. Maggy enables the replacement of the current waterfall development process for distributed ML applications, where code is rewritten at every stage, with an iterative development process. Maggy will fix for you the

different configuration parameters and workflow steps that differ when running your code on your laptop or in a cluster environment.

Figure 23 - Oblivious training function

In order to make Deep Learning models more robust and explainable, a new best practice, called ablation studies has evolved that is in nature similar to hyperparameter search experiments. Ablation studies require many trials to evaluate the relative contribution of different architectural and regularization components to models' performance. As we can see in the figures 24 and 25, Maggy employs two types of ablation studies. The first one involves changing the structure of the input - feature ablation and it involves dropping certain features from the input in order to see if the feature has any role in the output model's accuracy. The second one changes the structure of the model - layer ablation, and it involves dropping layers from the model in order to see if there is any impact on model performance.

Figure 24 - Feature Ablation

Figure 25 - Layer Ablation

3.7 Model serving and monitoring

Hopsworks currently supports SKLearn Model Serving[40], using Flask Servers which can be deployed either in Docker Containers or on Kubernetes, as well as Tensorflow Model Serving using TFServing[41] which can run in Docker Containers, Kubernetes or KFServing[42].

Once the models are served within Hopsworks, one can use the Hopsworks REST API for submitting inference requests to the serving servers. If during the serving instance creation you have specified a Kafka Topic to log the inference requests, each request will be logged in the topic.

By default, each project gets a default inference schema, depicted in figure 26. The schema is used to store the inference requests in Apache Kafka in a structured way, so that client applications can then read in real-time the inference requests and apply some business logic on how the model is performing.

s

Figure 26 - Inference Avro[43] Schema

Figure 27 - Model monitoring and logging architecture

Figure 27 depicts the overall architecture of model serving and monitoring in Hopsworks. In figure 28, we can see some of the benefits of monitoring models being served in production. Monitoring thus allows us to compare to models being served, rollback or fallback to a different model if model performance degrades as well as do gradual deployment where only parts of the inference requests are served to the new model and compared to the old model version until confidence is high enough to mode all inference requests to the new model. The model monitoring can also influence the model experimentation phase where the next version of this model is being designed or the model training phase where a critical issue detected with a current model version can cause a rollback to the previous version and the re-training of the current model.

Figure 28 - Model Serving and Monitoring workflow

3.8 Machine learning pipeline orchestration

All previous sections have demonstrated how to apply transformations and processing steps to data in order to go from raw data into an ML model. Most of these steps are repetitive and should be automated and managed by software tools.

Airflow is a platform to programmatically schedule and monitor workflows. It is built on top of three core concepts that we use in the Hopsworks Pipeline orchestration[44]: DAGs, Operators, and Tasks. A Direct Acyclic Graph(DAG) is a model of the tasks you wish to run defined in Python. This graph clearly defines the dependencies between the tasks. Operators define what a task should actually execute.

Figure 29 shows the main stages of a ML pipeline, which include a data ingestion and preparation stages, a feature engineering stage, a model training stage and a model serving stage. Each of these stages can actually contain multiple Airflow tasks.

Figure 29 - Airflow orchestration of a End to End ML Pipeline

4. HEAP Metadata

4.1 Hopsworks Metadata

Within the Hopsworks platform we save both the user metadata and the file system metadata within the same database. As we can see in figure 30, our filesystem, HopsFS, maintains its internal metadata in our database RonDB and we use the same database to store our user metadata associated with different files. This allows the platform to easily keep the data and metadata parts of the platform consistent. This means that when a machine learning artifact which can be a file, or a directory is deleted, its metadata is implicitly deleted too and we are never left with orphaned metadata.

Figure 30 - Scalable and Consistent Metadata in Hopsworks

Within the platform metadata is split into two types:

- Metadata that is managed by Hopsworks. Certain operations that the user does will use this metadata, so the user can read it, but modifying or deleting it is something that only the platform manages and not the user.
- Metadata that is completely controlled by the user. Here it is up to the user to create, read, update, delete (crud) the metadata. Any user that has access to the

file that the metadata is attached to, will also have the rights to do crud operations on the metadata.

The user-definable metadata that can be attached to files and directories are specified in Hopsworks as tags. A tag is a {key: value} association, that is linked to a file and is supposed to provide some additional information about it, for example, geographic origin. This is a mechanism that can provide more context to your data making it easier to share and discover it.

A tag value is defined as a schematized json. The schema of a tag value can be seen as a type for that particular value. So one tag schema can be used to validate multiple tag values, and thus within the platform we associate a tag key to a specific schema. This means that any time a tag for a specific key is associated with a file, the tag value will be checked for validity against the json schema associated with the key. Thus one can see tags as a triplet {key, schema, value}. The schema however is defined once, prior to any value being created, in Hopsworks by a user with administrator privileges since this schema will be available cluster wide. When the schema is created the cluster is aware of the {key : schema}. Any user can later on check the schemas available on the cluster and attach to files tags that adhere to the schema. The user will provide the {key : value} and the system will use the key to identify the schema and then use it to validate the value provided by the user.

Schemas follow <https://json-schema.org> as reference. The schemas define legal jsons and these can be primitives, objects or arrays. The schemas themselves are also defined as jsons.

Allowed primitive types are:

- string
- boolean
- integer
- number (float)

A tag of primitive type - string would look like:

```
{ "type" : "string" }
```

This schema would allow the following json value to be attached as a tag value:

```
Private Information
```

We can also define arbitrarily complex json schemas, such as:

```
{
```

```

"type" : "object",
"properties" : {
  "first_name" : { "type" : "string" },
  "last_name" : { "type" : "string" },
  "age" : { "type" : "integer" },
  "hobbies" : {
    "type" : "array",
    "items" : { "type" : "string" }
  }
},
"required" : ["first_name", "last_name", "age"],
"additionalProperties": false
}

```

A value that follows this schema would be:

```

{
  "first_name" : "John",
  "last_name" : "Doe",
  "age" : 27,
  "hobbies" : ["tennis", "reading"]
}

```

There are a number of sections of the json schema that are used extensively and will be explained in a bit more detail next.

Properties section of a tag is a dictionary that defines field names and types.

Json schemas are pretty lenient, all that the properties section tells us is that if a field appears, it should be of the appropriate type. If the json object contains the field first_name, this field cannot be of type boolean, it has to be of type string. What we emphasize here, is that the properties section does not impose that fields declared are mandatory, or that the json object cannot contain other fields that were not defined in the schemas.

Required section enforces the mandatory fields. In our case above, first_name, last_name, age are declared as mandatory, while the hobbies field is left as optional.

Additional Properties section enforces the strictness of the schema. If we set this to false the json objects of this schema can only use fields that are declared (mandatory or optional) by the schema. No undeclared fields will be allowed.

Type object is the default type for schemas, so you can omit it if you want to keep the schema short.

We can use additional properties of schemas as defined by <https://json-schema.org> to enhance our previous person schema:

- Add a \$schema section to allow us to use more advanced features of the json schemas defined in later drafts. The default schema draft is 4 and we will use 7 here (latest).
- Add an id field that is of type string but has to follow a particular regex pattern. We will also make this field mandatory.
- Set some rules on age, for example age should be an Integer between 0 and 150.
- Add an address field that is itself an object.

```
{
  "$schema": "http://json-schema.org/draft-07/schema#",
  "type": "object",
  "properties": {
    {
      "id": {
        "type": "string",
        "pattern": "^[A-Z]{2}[0-9]{4}$"
      },
      "first_name": { "type": "string" },
      "last_name": { "type": "string" },
      "age": {
        "type": "integer",
        "minimum": 0,
        "maximum": 150
      },
      "hobbies": {
        "type": "array",
        "items": { "type": "string" }
      },
      "address": {
        "street": { "type": "string" },
        "city": { "type": "string" }
      }
    },
    "required": ["id", "first_name", "last_name", "age"],
    "additionalProperties": false
  }
}
```

A valid value according to this new schema would be:

```
{
  "id": "AB1234",
  "first_name": "John",
  "last_name": "Doe",
  "age": 27,
  "hobbies": ["tennis", "reading"],
  "address": {
    "street": "Vasagatan nr. 12",
    "city": "Stockholm"
  }
}
```

This tag mechanism has been implemented in the Hopsworks platform as part of the task 6.2

4.2 Hopsworks Metadata Search

Datasets and ML artifacts such as feature groups, training datasets, models and experiments have a title, description and a number of tags attached to them. All of these are considered metadata and are part of an Elasticsearch index that is used in the UI for artifact discoverability through full text search.

By default all metadata associated to a dataset or to ML artifacts is public unless the user opts out. By making all metadata within the cluster public, we allow any user to be able to discover artifacts and datasets, even if they are not part of a project that she has access to. The user will not have access to the data, but through the metadata she will be able to discover the data and then ask the owner of the data for permission to use it.

4.3 HEAP Data Model

The HEAP project will process heterogeneous research data from different areas: genomics, epigenomics, metagenomics, clinical/medical data, consumer data and data from wearable sensors.

In order to integrate different data sources, a metadata model is designed for each area and a high level metadata will be supported by the platform to define general and common attributes shared by the datasets.

In principle, Hopsworks will process datasets containing files. A file has associated attributes common to most of the datasets and also specific attributes defining the singularities of the data.

Figure 31 - The FILE is the central entity belonging to a STUDY, being created by a CREATOR. It is produced through a LAB ANALYSIS (e.g.,DNA extraction) and the analyses done (for instance, bioinformatics analyses) are defined in ANALYSIS. The FILE can have as ORIGIN another file that follows the same model.

The following table 1 provides the metadata (entities with its attributes) representing high-throughput data in HEAP. The Dataset and the Study are implicit objects in the Hopsworks models. Study is a Project with extended attributes. Most of the attributes are text, with exception of some numeric and date/time types.

Entity	Attribute	Description
Person	Person ID	
Person	First Name	First Name of the creator
Person	Last name	Last name of the creator
Person	email	email of the creator
Person	Address	
Person	Phone	

Researcher	Researcher ID	
Researcher	Person ID	
Researcher	Institution	
Dataset	Dataset ID	GPU (doi) of the dataset stored in the IC
Dataset	Dataset Name	Dataset Name assigned by the dataset responsible
Dataset	Responsible	Responsible person for the dataset (data controller)
Dataset	Location	Complete path to the dataset (URI)
Dataset	Date of creation	Date of creation of the dataset in the system
Dataset	Description	Description of the dataset
Dataset	Keywords	Keywords for easy query
File	FileID	PUI of the file (ID, url, etc.)
File	Dataset ID	GPU (doi) of the dataset where the file belong to
File	File Name	Complete file name
File	File Format	Format of the file (normally the extension) from the list "File Format"
File	Creation date	Date when the file was created in the system (OS file attribute)
File	Parent File ID	PUI of file used to generate this file (if exists). It can be several parent files (list of IDs)
File	Data Category	As in list "Data Category"
File	Description	Free text to describe the file
Creator	Research ID	Contact Information ID of the creator of the file is stored in the system
Study	StudyID	PUI of the Study (project)
Study	Contact Information ID	Contact Information ID of the study as stored in the system (user account)

		info)
Study	Study name	Study name
Study	Study Acronym	Study Acronym
Study	Description	Description
Study	Principal Investigator	Principal Investigator
Study	Keywords	list of keywords separated by comma
Lab Analysis	Lab Analysis ID	
Lab Analysis	Lab Analysis type	Type of lab analysis as in Lab Analysis List
Lab Analysis	Level 1	analysis name: analysis type
Lab Analysis	Level 2	analysis name: analysis type
Lab Analysis	Level 3	analysis name: analysis type
Lab Analysis	Level 4	analysis name: analysis type
Lab Analysis	Level 5	analysis name: analysis type
Lab Analysis	Date	Analysis date of last process
Origin	Origin ID	
Origin	Origin Type	As in list Origin Type
Origin	Origin ID	ID of the origin (sample ID, participant iD, file ID, DatasetID, etc.)
Origin	Level 1	Origin: Origin type
Origin	Level 2	Origin: Origin type
Origin	Level 3	Origin: Origin type
Origin	Level 4	Origin: Origin type
Origin	Level 5	Origin: Origin type
Origin	Origin Description	Free text describing the origin
Instrument	Instrument ID	
Instrument	Instrument Name	
Instrument	Vendor	
Instrument	Protocol	
Analysis	Analysis ID	(Experiment)
Analysis	Software Name	

Analysis	Version	
Analysis	GitHub	
Analysis	Result Type	
Analysis	Link to Result	
Analysis	Result summary	

Table 1. Entities and attributes for the HEAP generic data model. Implicit entities in Hopsworks are in red text. Values from defined lists are in green text. Lab Analysis and Origin entities have custom attributes depending of the area of the data (genomics, epigenomics, metagenomics, clinical/medical data, consumer data and data from wearable sensors)

At the moment, Hopsworks implements the metadata for sequencing data. The attributes and standard vocabulary lists describe mostly sequencing data. However, the aim is to have an integrated metadata model that allows synergy between datasets.

In order to use a standardised vocabulary, some attribute values are defined. The following table 2 shows lists associated with some attribute values.

List	Value Level 1
Data Category	Clinical history/Medical Records
Data Category	Genotyping array
Data Category	Sequencing raw reads
Data Category	Bioinformatics analysis
Data Category	Survey data
Data Category	Imaging data
Data Category	Transcriptome profiling
Data Category	DNA methylation
Data Category	Biospecimen
Data Category	Survey data
Data Category	Physiological/Biochemical measurements
File Format	txt
File Format	fastq
File Format	Bam
File Format	csv
File Format	m8
File Format	fasta

File Format	tab
File Format	sam
Lab Analysis Type	Clinical history/Medical Records
Lab Analysis Type	Genotyping array
Lab Analysis Type	Sequencing raw reads
Lab Analysis Type	Bioinformatic analysis
Origin Type	Sample
Origin Type	Participant
Origin Type	Dataset
Origin Type	File
Sample Type	Whole blood
Sample Type	Plasma
Sample Type	Serum
Sample Type	Urine
Sample Type	Stool
Sample Type	CSF
Sample Type	Nasal
Sample Type	Cervical swab
Sample Type	Cervical smear
Sample Type	Cervical cells
Sample Type	Saliva
Sample Type	Sputum
Sample Type	FFPE
Sample Type	Tissue
Sample Type	Tissue slide
Sex	female
Sex	male
Sex	other
Age Unit	Days
Age Unit	Weeks
Age Unit	Months
Age Unit	Years
Extraction type	DNA
Extraction type	RNA

Table 3. List values for attributes

HEAP also will process datasets that are not associated with files. For instance, the Consumer Cohort provides records of purchased items and descriptions of the items. In this case, datasets about the consumed items are provided to Hopsworks to be stored in the Hive database and Feature Store.

4.4 HEAP Catalog

The HEAP data catalogue is essential to fulfill first, the “F” of the FAIR principles, i.e. to find the cohorts and records, and when they are found to get the appropriate information for the “A”, “I” and “R” principles¹. When talking about catalogues we have to distinguish the following categories:

Purpose / Intended Use of the Catalogue

The functionalities of a catalogue depend - beside some technical and data protection issues - mainly on the intended use. We foresee the following scenarios within HEAP:

- **Find** a specific object and get the appropriate metadata for access and use. For this the HEAP catalogues have to contain the necessary search index, e.g. provided by solutions such as ElasticSearch and a search interface. The result of a search operation can be very minimal, i.e. just indicating the existence and an approx. number of objects (discovery mode) or provide a rich set of attributes and optionally the (digital) assets themselves. A discovery mode is used, if the catalogue describes sensitive and personal (data) objects.
- **Visualize** and describe what is in the HEAP data warehouse and information commons, e.g. a sample collection in a biobank, a patient registry and most important the results of the HEAP research projects. In this scenario, the user gets an overview and can browse through the collection. Such a feature is in particular important to advertise and to report the assets of HEAP. Principles of descriptive statistics and visual analytics will be used to build catalogue dashboards, e.g. with the use of the Kibana dashboard tool in task 7.5.
- **Monitor** quality parameters and provenance information objects in a collection. Such parameters cover e.g. preanalytical attributes for sample collections, metadata to monitor data quality up to a full chain of sample and data provenance (workflow information) for objects of the HEAP information commons.

Granularity of the Catalogue

¹ Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse of digital assets.

A catalogue describes a cohort at the **resource level** giving an aggregated view on what is in a collection, or at **record level**, describing the specific objects (samples, donores, digital assets) in detail. In case of a biobank catalogue, the resource level is the level 1 & 2 and the record level is 3 as shown in figure 32, see also [45]. Depending on the intended use as well as IPR and data protection restrictions the right granularity has to be chosen.

Figure 32 - Different levels of a biobanking catalogue[45]

For the HEAP information commons, a record level catalogue will be provided for internal use directly integrated into the HEAP data warehouse and long term storage solutions. In addition, a resource level catalogue will be available for external and public use and a catalogue of catalogues will provide the highest level to find the right entry door into the HEAP information commons.

Interface to the Catalogue

The interface to a catalogue is either provided for **humans** with a graphical user interface or for **machines** with a so-called application programmers interface (API). HEAP will provide both interfaces and, according to the FAIR principles, use common ontologies and APIs to make all catalogues fully accessible by global indexing services. [46] Our APIs will be based on the [FAIR Data Point “API”](#) [47] using as the core metadata standard DCAT3 and [Dublin Core](#), combined with the [Linked Data Platform \(LDP\)](#). Figure 33 illustrates how the catalogues for the HEAP data warehouse and information commons and the HEAP catalogue of catalogues will be implemented by task 7.5 in close cooperation with WP6.

Figure 33 - Fair data points as interface to HEAP catalogs and to a catalogue of catalogues

5. Knowledge Engine integration with Information Commons

The Knowledge Engine (KE) is the layer that performs all the data science and analytics work and of course it requires access to all necessary datasets including the sensitive datasets stored in the Information Commons (IC). As such, as part of task 6.1 we have defined our integration plan between the Hopsworks as the platform implementing the KE and the IC provided services. This plan includes five steps:

1. Integration with the authentication services of IC. In short we Hopsworks should use the same service to get users to login as IC.
2. Integration with the authorization services of IC. In short synchronize what datasets a user can view and use depending on the permissions defined in IC.
3. Integration of the data access through a FUSE client. In short, access sensitive data on demand, transparently to the user and without duplicating into KE.
4. Integration of the data publishing to IC. Once sensitive data is produced in Hopsworks provides an easy mechanism to upload the data, together with the metadata to the IC.
5. Deploy HEAP platform in the secured, air gapped environment provided by CSC (the secure environment is provided by CSC ePouta[15] virtual private cloud).

Step 1 is completed and deployed on the testbed (for this environment we make use of CSC cPouta[16], which is the public cloud infrastructure). Step 2 is currently being evaluated before being released on the testbed. Steps 3,4,5 are planned, but not yet implemented.

5.1 HEAP Testbed

A testbed is deployed at <https://86.50.253.93:8181/hopsworks>. When accessing the testbed, the user is currently faced with a "Your connection is not private" warning. This is due to the use of a self signed certificate by the Hopsworks platform. The user can continue to the testbed by either:

- clicking advance and then proceeding
- if running from chrome browser, you can click anywhere on the screen and type "thisisunsafe" - one word, no spaces. This is a chrome browser developer trick, where if you know the site is safe, you can bypass the certificate check. You can read more here:

<https://medium.com/@idomo/chrome-bypassing-ssl-certificate-check-2-f8eb6c2be68a>

We will soon get a signed certificate for the project's domain, which should allow us to now show this warning message anymore.

The testbed instance is deployed on the CSC Openstack infrastructure and consists of one main node, which contains all the data storage, all the services required to make the platform operational, but minimal computational resources. This node is on at all times and it is enough to perform "hello world" like examples. For proper experimentation, we can dynamically bring additional computational nodes. These nodes are stateless, they store no data, and thus can easily be made to join or leave the cluster. These nodes, we will call workers and they come in 3 different flavours:

- small - 8vcores, 32 GB memory.
- medium - 18 vcores, 72GB memory.
- large - 38 vcores, 152GB memory.

We have chosen these sizes as the large node type is close to the biggest, the infrastructure can handle and can be used to test computational tasks that cannot currently be split into smaller chunks. The small variant is there in order to test the distributive nature of different tasks and to check if the communication between workers within the job works as intended. As such we have currently tested with up to 6 small workers.

5.2 Hopsworks integration with IC Authentication Clients

The first stage of the integration plan is complete and currently deployed on the testbed instance. This step includes the integration between Hopsworks Authentication and the CSC Authentication Clients and for this we have added support in Hopsworks for two OAuth2 Clients used within CSC, one of them is the Elixir Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (<https://elixir-europe.org/services/compute/aai>) and the second one is a test client based on the internal CSC Authentication and Authorization client.

The OAuth2 Clients can be configured within the Hopsworks Administration Menus as can be seen in figure 34, in the *Register OAuth 2.0 Client* section.

Figure 34 - Hopworks Administration Menu

In this section, we can add the configuration to connect to both OAuth2 Clients as can be seen in figure 35.

Registered OAuth2 server												
id	Client id	Client secret	Provider name	Provider display name	Provider logo URI	Provider URI	Provider Metadata Endpoint	Authorisation Endpoint	Token Endpoint	Userinfo Endpoint	JWKS URI	
2	b02ccba4867cf32dd85	[REDACTED]	Heap CSC	Heap CSC		https://test-user-auth.csc.fv	true					[edit] [delete]
1	c52aa021-924b-4d8d-b920-1d123117d2fe	[REDACTED]	Elixir	Heap Elixir		https://login.elixir-czech.org/oauth/	true					[edit] [delete]

Figure 35 - Elixir and CSC Authentication Clients Configuration

After the two clients are configured, the login page of Hopworks will also provide as possible login methods, authentication with Elixir or with CSC instead of the default Hopworks email/password authentication, as can be seen in figures 36, 37, 38.

HOPSWORKS
ENTERPRISE EDITION

SIGN IN TO CONTINUE.

Email

Password

Need support? Login help?

Login

Heap CSC

Heap Elixir

Register

Figure 36 - Hopsworks Login

elixir

Choose how to log in

use your previous selection

Google

or

Sign in using another institute or account

Figure 37 - Elixir Authentication Client Integration

Figure 38 - CSC Authentication Client Integration

5.3 Hopsworks integration with IC data authorization

As part of the HEAP platform, the REMS system manages the access of every user to the sensitive datasets. As such, we need to mirror these access rights within Hopsworks, so that users are not hindered when accessing sensitive data within their workflows as long as they have the appropriate access correctly defined in REMS. This integration between REMS and Hopsworks should be as seamless as possible and changes from REMS should be reflected in Hopsworks and changes in Hopsworks should be checked against REMS. Since there can be multiple instances of REMS running we will instead interact with the AAI system which will provide us with an aggregation of all the REMS instances' permissions.

There are Hopsworks workflows that would be affected by this integration and these are: adding a member to a project, adding an sensitive dataset to a project or sharing an sensitive dataset with another project. The AAI system provides a REST API that

can be queried by Hopsworks to collect the required information, which means Hopsworks will employ a pull mechanism to synchronize with AAI.

The first case of adding a new user to a project is presented in figure 39. In this case, in order to ensure a normal workflow for the new user, we should check that this new user has access to all sensitive datasets. If there are sensitive datasets in the project, including shared ones, that the user does not have rights to access, the membership change operation will fail with a message listing all datasets that cannot be accessed by the new user. The user is now expected to apply for the appropriate permissions in the appropriate REMS instances and once the user has access to all sensitive datasets, the operation to add the user to the project's team can be reattempted.

Figure 39 - Add a member to a project

The second case, presented in figure 40, involves adding a new sensitive dataset to an existing project. The same check has to be done at this point but from the perspective of the whole project team. We have to check that all members of a project have access to the new sensitive dataset defined in one REMS instance before adding the dataset to the project. In case some of the users don't have access, the add dataset operation will fail with a list of users that do not have appropriate permissions. These users will need to apply for correct permission in REMS and then the add dataset operation can be retried.

Figure 40 - Add a sensitive dataset to a project

The third case involves the mechanism for sharing datasets in Hopsworks. In order to support collaboration, we want to allow sharing of sensitive datasets between projects, as long as the REMS permissions allow this. Figure 41 shows the workflow in this case, which is similar to the first case where we were trying to add a member to a project. In this case, we have to check that the members of the project we want to share a sensitive dataset with, all have the permissions to access it. In case they don't, the sharing operation will be stuck in pending mode and a message will be sent to each of the members that do not have correct permissions, in order to apply for them in the appropriate REMS instance. Once all members have applied, the sharing of the dataset can be accepted by data owners in the target project. As long as at least one member of the project doesn't have the correct permissions, the operation will remain in pending mode.

Figure 41 - Share a dataset with another project

Since we are employing a pull mechanism from Hopsworks side, in order to synchronize with REMS, there are of course cases when we might be out of sync because the operation was initiated from REMS and Hopsworks is not aware of it. This is the case of revoking a user's permission to access a particular sensitive dataset. In this case, the user would still be able to see the footprint of the sensitive dataset in Hopsworks, but she will not be able to view the contents of the dataset or run applications that make use of the specific dataset. This behaviour would trigger a possibly unexpected behaviour and thus we would like to correct this as soon as possible. If the user is not expected to have the right to use this sensitive dataset, it would probably be the case that she should be removed from the project. For this reason, as we show in figure 42, we run a periodic check on the integrity of projects containing sensitive datasets, where we check that all members still have access to all sensitive datasets contained in the project. If a user is detected as not having permission to a sensitive dataset, both the user and the project owner will be informed about this and expected to either fix the permission or remove the user from the project team.

Figure 42- Periodic check on project integrity

5.4 Hopsworks integration with access to Sensitive Data in IC

Hopsworks, as the implementation of the Knowledge Engine, performs all the data engineering and machine learning computations and as such requires access to the sensitive datasets stored in the Information Commons. However, the datasets are not duplicated in Hopsworks' own storage and instead they are accessed on demand through a FUSE client provided by the CSC. Each computation running in Hopsworks will have access through this FUSE client to the sensitive datasets that the user who started the application has access to. Based on the previous integration with AAI, all users within a project, the project users, will have access to the same subset of sensitive datasets, and thus any member of the project can re-run the application and there is no risk of the application not having access to all required data.

5.5 Hopsworks integration with data publishing to IC

Hopsworks, as the Knowledge Engine, is intended to analyse sensitive data and provide useful insights, in some cases these insights might be new datasets, aggregations of others, that can be reused in other research projects. As such these datasets can be published, together with their metadata to the Information Commons. During the publishing process, a person will be marked as the data custodian of this new dataset and will be the person responsible for providing access to others to the dataset through appropriate permissions set in REMS. This metadata can be further pushed to the HEAP Catalog for easy discoverability of datasets.

5.6 Deploy HEAP platform to air gapped environment

In order to test the final version of the platform, which will be fully secured, we will need to move the testbed towards an air gapped environment - this is an environment with no access to the internet, or access that is tightly monitored and proxied and monitored at all times. CSC infrastructure offers two Openstack environments called cPouta and ePouta. The cPouta is the public cloud which can be easily accessed from the Internet. The ePouta cloud is a virtual private cloud designed to meet the security requirements of handling sensitive data. As the first step in testing and using the HEAP platform, the testbed is deployed to the public cPouta cloud, with plans to soon move it to the private, secure ePouta cloud and start using the platform with sensitive data.

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